

Radical Interaction: a podcast of interaction exchange

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Abstract

This work compiles *radical interaction* a series of interviews with NIME and HCI researchers. Inspired by the timely arrival of alt-NIME, we look at alternative methods of bringing our work to NIME, presenting a series of eight audio interviews as an online interactive website, that plays with this year's theme of *community*. We present a standard linear view of the episodes, alongside a shared listening experience, where a community of listeners interact with each other through an entangled listening experience that changes, depending on how many concurrent listeners are actively listening. An accompanying zine, circulated in physical form at the conference, guides listeners through the processes and ideas of the podcast, but also is manifested digitally for the its premier at NIME'26, as a tool for engaging with shared listening experience.

1 Project Description

radical interaction is a podcast series that is inspired through the lens of research and interaction. Focusing on NIME researchers as a set of eight interviews with broad participant interests, ranging from PhD students, established researchers, to well known artists. The episodes are ordered as follows:

- (1) prologue
- (2) rodrigo constanzo
- (3) courtney reed
- (4) sarah angliss
- (5) jasmine, maisie, patricia
- (6) kathy hinde
- (7) atau tanaka
- (8) epilogue

With the first and last episodes bookending the series, with an introduction and closing thoughts, respectively.

Radical interaction as idea came about when the first two authors pondered on the idea interviewing researchers in the field of NIME and more generally HCI. It was inspired by chats over lunch, often while arguing about the use of defraction as a tool for research. It lead us to wonder if we could expand our discussions to a wider group and it has been amazing to spend time with people whose work we have often considered from afar, or in some cases close up, as with our own PhD students. We hope that these reflections and discussions are of interest to the wider NIME community.

With this submission, we aim to bridge the discussions that happen in reasearch labs, cafes, and other places where NIMEers meet and formal presentations limited to papers and other traditional research outputs. NIME 2026's theme

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Fig. 1. Frontside of the A2 Radical Interaction Zine

of community and the launch of alt-NIME, offers a chance to bridge these worlds, providing alternative means of communicating knowledge and understanding. We present this work as community made, with unconventional outputs, a series of podcast episodes, a communal listening experience, and physical paper zine. This work aims to frame research in NIME as a community activity, that lives in our connections, in our labs, in our cafes, and in the halls of NIME itself.

1.1 Physical Outputs

To keep with the spirit of the podcast and its intention to break with podcast norms, we explore the idea of a podcast as zine, delivered both in traditional paper format and digitally, and the listening experience itself can be individual or shared. Our submission includes the podcast episodes, a physical zine, that is two sides of A2, folded to form a book, along with a webapp. A digital version of the zine is integrated into the webapp, to be traversed with the physical zine in hand, but listened to through live audio mixing, that varies depending on the number of active listeners. (This part of the work will premier at NIME'26.)

The digital zine is delivered as a webapp that works in two modes; mode one presents the podcast through a community listening approach, using server we developed to manage the shared listening experience; while mode two presents a conventional linear listening, where each episode is presented.

2 Technical Notes

If accepted *radical interaction* at NIME'26 would be presented throughout the conference! Distributed as a physical zine, with 200 hard copies brought to NIME itself,

3 Media Links

The *radical interaction* website can be found at the following link:

- Video: <https://radicalinteraction.org>

For this submission we have made the linear view, accessed through the bottom image on the landing page, live, the podcasts can be listened through, as expected. The community listening experience is in place, however, the backend server, required for shared state, is currently not running, and will instead be active during the conference itself. This allows it to be premiered at NIME'26.

The zine, in PDF format, is provided in the supplemental material, along with a video showing the folding and unfolding of a printed copy of the zine.

4 Ethical Standards

This work was ethically approved by University of West of England's Faculty Research Ethics Committee, and all interviewees are also co-authors of this submission. AI was not used in the creation of this research.

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Acknowledgments

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- [3] Merlin Wizard. 2022. *Advanced Spellcasting for Beginners: A Practical Guide*. Hogwarts Press, Diagon Alley. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-9876543210>
Plus, some citations to articles: [1–3].

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